

Environmental Impact on the Activities of Enterprises Associated With High Energy Intensity of Production of Innovative Products

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Abstract: *The article examines the features of the energy saving regulation mechanism at industrial enterprises. The features of the formation of innovative products of industrial enterprises are considered. The main tasks, including indirect and direct ones, capable of creating conditions for energy saving are identified. An energy saving mechanism is proposed and effective levers are given that regulate the saving of energy resources at industrial enterprises.*

Key words: *financial resources, resources, energy saving, direct tasks, investment activities of enterprises, analysis, indirect tasks, efficiency.*

Introduction

One of the main factors of economic development of enterprises in all spheres of the economy is the presence of an innovative management system focused on stable development based on saving labor costs and energy conservation, based on the assessment of the use of resource potential. Because the innovative development of an enterprise uses funds and natural resources of a production and non-production nature. Their main elements are: raw materials, water resources and energy resources. At the same time, in the structure of natural resources, energy conservation is a priority.

There is no enterprise that does not use energy resources. But how are energy resources used? What can result from the careless attitude of individuals and legal entities to energy of all types, in particular, energy. Studying the state of energy use and identifying possible options for saving energy resources without harming the activities of enterprises and their financial condition is an acute problem. The attention of all entities in the last year has been focused specifically on saving energy resources.

Analysis of literature, materials, methods.

The problems of energy supply were studied by such scientists as V.N.Avdeenko, V.A.Kotlov [1], A.G.Aganbegyan [2], B.T.Kliyanenko [3]. The greatest contribution to the study of this phenomenon in the context of its environmental significance was made in their scientific works by: V.V.Buzyrev [4], I.P.Nuzhina [5], L.A.Kaverzina [6], K.Zalman [7] and others. At the same time, most of the works of these scientists, although devoted to the efficiency of using energy resources by industrial enterprises, do not pay attention to the practical implementation of proposals for their use by innovative enterprises. Also unstudied are the issues of efficient use of energy resources by the population and service sector entities. Their economical use of energy resources is difficult to control. A significant disruption in the use of energy resources affects the production activities of innovative enterprises. They often face a negative phenomenon: power outages for the purpose of normal power supply to important enterprises. Sometimes individual rural areas are left without energy, which affects the ecological state of the agricultural products they produce. Such a listing of authors is unacceptable. It is recommended to indicate a specific author and the purpose and achievement of his research. It is not recommended to use the terms *foreign* and *domestic*.

Purpose of the study.

The aim of the study is to develop a mechanism for saving energy resources on the part of its consumers.

In accordance with the stated goal, the following tasks are solved in the work: the essence, significance, and problems of developing the phenomenon of the financial mechanism for regulating energy saving are considered; the main criteria and options for choosing a mechanism for economical regulation of energy consumption are identified.

Analysis.

As follows from the results of the analysis of economic literature, the problem of developing a financial mechanism for the use of energy resources is not new. Considering the activities of innovative enterprises, it should be clarified that they include entities associated with investing in enterprises in the conditions of post-industry. Touching upon the latter, we have made an attempt to substantiate the methodological basis of this concept. The concept of "post-industry" has replaced the term "modernization, reconstruction". Post-industry in its modern understanding means a set of industries characterized by close stable technical and technological ties, covering the entire stage of work on the creation of innovative manufacturing enterprises.

The post-industrial economy and its subsystem include investors interested in investing funds in investment projects; the banking sector, the purpose of which is to finance the development of the post-industrial economy.

The basis of the post-industrial economy is a subsystem that covers enterprises of all spheres of the economy, functioning in the interrelation of enterprises included in industrial production. The development of production specialization, its consistent industrialization lead to the division of production into sub-sectors.

The post-industrial economy is all the more important because issues of its development until recently remained primarily a subject of research by economists from industrially developed countries.

In a post-industrial economy, energy saving is the main one, which includes a set of technical and technological measures aimed at the effective (or economical) use of resources. This can be achieved by switching to new technologies in order to ensure energy saving.

However, in each case, energy saving measures can be divided into :

- organizational and technical, which involve compliance with operating modes, ensuring an optimal level of loading of production equipment, and timely completion of ongoing capital and restoration work;
- innovation and investment (technical and technological), associated with the replacement of obsolete production capacities, the introduction of modern energy-efficient technology, and the modernization of technological processes and technologies.

The value of measures should be determined both by the practice of implementing investment projects and by indicators of energy efficiency growth.

The tasks of regulating energy supply to enterprises can be presented in Fig. 1.

The presented model of energy use includes: tasks, levers and regulation mechanisms (indirect).

In this case, special attention should be paid to energy consumption (EC), which is associated with the accounting, control and analysis of EP.

The model of the sequence of work organization in time and its connections with the standardization of EP and energy use (EI_{sp}) is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Model of energy saving and analysis of its use consumers

The expansion of the range of energy saving (ES) methods is a subject of discussion. Most experts propose as a tool for forming the ES criterion the integral indicator ($\int$) of the uniformity (rhythm) of the production process in the main technological processes [8]. For the energy consumer, this indicator is determined by comparing a set of private indicators of the enterprise task:

$$\int P_{i\text{production.}} = P_{pr1} \cdot P_{pr2} \cdot P_{pr3} \cdot \dots \cdot P_{prn}, \quad (1)$$

где: $P_{i\text{production.}}$ - integral indicator of production of the i -th division; $P_{pr1}, \dots, P_{prn}$ - indicators of the production process; $\int P$ - fulfillment of established tasks.

The reduction ($\downarrow$) of the level (Δ)of energy consumption (EC) is ensured by reserves of deviations $\int \Pi$ of the production process. The reserve (P) of possible increase $\int \Pi$ is defined as the difference between the maximum achieved and actual uniformity:

$$P_{lvl} = P_d \uparrow - P_{fact} \cdot (2)$$

In practice, impact assessment $\int P$ level (Δ)electricity consumption is recommended to be solved by using a correlation-regression model, which means establishing a relationship between specific energy costs P_{fact} and a set of factors, where it is possible to introduce an integral ($\int$) indicator ($\int P$). In addition, another method of energy saving is presented in the economic literature, which is based on leveling the consumption of electrical energy by changing the operating schedule of enterprises [g].

Conclusion

ESB must be managed not only during the production of products of enterprises, but also directly in the production process, that is, during the construction of industrial, transport, agricultural, housing, social and cultural and household facilities. When constructing various production facilities, it is recommended to actively use ESB-managing measures.

As a result of the conducted study of the ESB, the degree of energy resource savings at the enterprise was determined. The mechanism of the ESB at the enterprise should include the main components: direct tasks, levers and indirect tasks, energy savings, as well as EI tasks.

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